

Overview and Review of the Taa Language: Background and Linguistic Features

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A product of Lost Worlds Institute

What is the Taa language? - The Taa language, part of the Tuu language family of Khoisan languages, is famous for having the largest consonant inventory in the world. It includes about 122 consonants, 44 vowels, and a total of 45 sounds. Taa incorporates two dialects: East Taa and West Taa. The name of the Taa itself translates to 'human being'.

When has it been documented? - Researchers began documenting East Taa in the 1970s, led by South African linguist Anthony Traill. Since 2004, linguists have investigated the West Taa dialect through a DOBES project, which continued until 2009.

Who currently speaks the Taa language? - Approximately 2,500–3,000 people (also known as San, Bushmen, or Basarwa) in Namibia and Botswana still speak Taa. These communities, historically hunter-gatherers, live in a wide area stretching from the Molopo River on the Botswana–South Africa border to Leonardville on the Nossob River in Namibia.

Where is Taa being spoken? - People speak Taa mainly in the Kalahari Desert of southern Africa.

Why is Taa going extinct? - The language faces extinction because of its low social status compared to other groups in Namibia and Botswana. Political, economic, and socio-linguistic marginalization, along with cultural assimilation, have reduced its use. As these pressures spread, the language retreats to only a few remaining strongholds.

Language Characteristics

The Taa language has:

- 161 segments/sounds
 - Contrastive use of clicks
 - Such as “tsk”, “tut”, or “clop” sounds
 - Six series of stops
 - Laryngeal settings/airstream mechanisms (such as voiceless vs voiced)
- 130 consonants
 - Uvular consonants
- 28 vowels

- 3 tones

In contrast, the **English** language only has:

- 40 segments/sounds
- 27 consonants
- 13 vowels

Grammar Overview

- **Word order:** In Taa, the basic order goes:

Subject → Predicate (what’s being said about the subject) → Object

In other words, the Taa language follows the SVO (Subject - Verb - Object) structure. If there’s supporting information (such as time, place, or manner), it usually comes at the end and is introduced with **adjuncts** (prepositions like “at,” “with,” “in”, etc.).

- **Nouns & agreement:** Nouns belong to different classes. Adjectives, pronouns, and verbs must agree with the noun’s class using special markers.
- Example:

èé sí glá-í màhrí kà àùtò kì Kòbààbè
 (“She sends the money to Gobabis by car.”)

Grammar Specifics

Chart produced by author:

Agreement classes	Agreement markers						
Class 1	i						
Classes 2i; 2ii	an [a/ã]						
Classes 3i; 3ii	e						
Class 4	u						
Class 5	nn [ŋ]/ng [ŋ]						
Type of Clicks	Symbols	Example					
Bilabial	⊙	'm⊙ài (tree,					

		wood)					
Dental	l	laa (go)					
Lateral	ll	llnaam (to be damp)					
Palatal	ɸ	ɸnaa (see)					
Alveolar	!	!Xoon (Taa)					
Types of Stops	Symbols		Singular	West !Xoon plural	East !Xoon plural		
Voicless (Tenuis)	/t/, /p/, /k/, /q/		àqà (Father)	àqà-rū	àqà-tû		
Voiced	/g/, /G/, /ts/, /p/		qàe (Mother)	qà-rú	qàe-tû		
Aspirated	/ph/, /th/, /kh/, /qh/		Ōàa (Child)	Ōōo-rù	Ōàa-tû		
Ejective	/t'/, /k'/, /q'/, /k'x'/		Ōqàqe (Child)	Ōqòqo-nù, Ōqòqo-rù	Ōqàqa-nî		
Aspirated cluster	/dth/, /dtsh/, /gkh/		'Inàn (Spouse)	'nlán-ú, 'nlá-rú	'Inàn-tû		
Ejective cluster	/dts'/, /gkx'/						
Fricatives (voiceless)	/f/, /s/, /x/, /h/						
Example:							
èé	sí	glá-í	màhrí	kà	áùtò	kì	Kòbààbè.
Class 3ii	Class 1	Class 1	Class 1	Class 2i	2ii	Class 1	Class 3ii
-		g = voiced stop		k = voiceless stop	-	k = voiceless stop	k = voiceless stop
She send the money to Gobabis by car							
Example:							
n	si	tana	ka	!Xuun	ɸaan.		

Class 5	Class 1	Class 2i	Class 2i	Class 5	Class 5		
-	-	t = voiceless stop	k = voiceless stop	! = alveolar click	ʘ = palatal click		
I speak the !Xoon (Taa) language							
Example:							
n	si	nlā-è	nʘàhrè	!xā-ē	ʘ'ū-ē		
Class 5	Class 1	Class 3i	Class 3i	Class 3i	Class 3i		
-	s = fricative	l = dental click	ʘ = palatal click	! = alveolar click	ʘ = palatal click		
I see one big sheep							

	Egressive			Ingressive (Clicks)					Egressive			
	Labial	Alveolar	Alveolar- Affricate / Palatal	Labial	Dental	Alveolar	Palatal	Lateral	Velar	Uvular	Uvular- Affricate	Glottal
Oral stops												
Plain	p	t	ts	⊙	l	!	ʘ	l	k	q		(')
Voiced	b	d	dz	g⊙	gl	g!	gʘ	gl	g	gq		
Vls. aspirated	ph	th	tsh	⊙h	lh	!h	ʘh	lh	kh	qh		
Voiced aspirated	bh	dh	dzh	g⊙h	glh	g!h	gʘh	glh	gh	gqh		
Voiceless ejective	p'	t'	ts'	⊙'	l'	!'	ʘ'	l'	k'	q'	qx'	
Voiced ejective			dz'		gl'	g!'	gʘ'	gl'	g'	gq'	gqx'	
Nasal stops												
Plain (voiced)	m	n~nn	ny	n⊙	nl	n!	nʘ	nl	ng			
Voiceless					nhl	nh!	nhʘ	nhl				
Glottalised	'm	'n		'n⊙	'nl	'n!	'nʘ	'nl				
Fricatives												
Plain (voiceless)	f	s								x		h
Sonorants												
Approximant	w		y									
Lateral approx.		l										
Tap		r										

- Since Taa is a SVO (Subject - Verb - Object) language, genitives, adjectives, relative clauses, and numbers come after the noun they apply to
 - There are 5 nominal agreement classes and 2 tone groups.
 - Agreement occurs on pronouns, transitive verbs (including the object), adjectives, prepositions, and some particles

- As described by a DOBES project, when C = consonant, V = vowel, and N = nasal stop, the Taa syllable structure may be of the following:
 - CVV
 - CCVV
 - CVC₂V
 - CCVC₂V
 - CVN
 - CCVN

Phonology

- Taa uses several distinct clicking sounds: bilabial, dental, lateral, alveolar, and palatal.
 - Bilabial (ʘ): Speakers make this rarest click with both lips.
 - Dental (ǀ): This click sounds like the familiar tut-tut or tsk-tsk.
 - Lateral (ǁ): This click resembles the sound equestrians use to communicate with horses.
 - Alveolar (ǃ): Speakers produce it by pressing the top of the tongue against the alveolar ridge.
 - Palatal (ǃ̟): This click comes from placing the flat tongue broadly on the palate.
- This click system works by combining each click type with a phonation accompaniment. Examples are plain, aspirated, nasal, and ejective.
- Taa is also a tonal language, utilizing pitch to convey meaning. The West !Xoon dialect has high and low tones (DoBES), while the East !Xoon dialect (Traill) uses four: high, low, mid, and mid-falling, marked as [áá], [àá], [àà], and [áà].
- Anthony Traill also noted how East !Xoon nouns divide into two groups:
 - Class I: causes nearby verbs/endings to sound level or rising.
 - Class II: has variable tonal effects.
- Taa has 5 vowels: a, e, i, o, u
 - Traill notes the phonotations of the East !Xoon dialect as plain ⟨a⟩, murmured ⟨ah⟩, or glottalized ⟨a̰⟩. [a o u] may also be both glottalized and murmured ⟨a'h⟩, as well as pharyngealized ⟨a̠⟩/⟨aq̠⟩ or strident ⟨a̠h⟩/⟨aq̠h⟩. [a u] may be both pharyngealized and glottalized ⟨a̠̰⟩, for 26 vowels excluding nasalization or length.

1) Taa has non-click consonants

•These are pulmonic (outgoing airstream) sounds across places of articulation: bilabial, dental/alveolar, post-alveolar, palatal, velar, uvular, and pharyngeal. Key series include:

•Stops: Plain (p, t, k), aspirated (p^h, t^h), ejective (p', t'), implosive (ɓ, ɗ), uvular (q, q^h, q').

•Fricatives: Voiceless (f, s, ʃ, x, ɬ), voiced (β, z, ʒ, ʁ, ʕ).

•Nasals: Plain (m, n, ŋ, ŋ), pre-stopped (ᵐp, ᵐt).

•Approximants: w, l, j, ʋ.

• Many have secondary features, e.g., labialized velar stop k^w or pharyngealized alveolar $t^ç$.

Gender Agreement

- Nouns are divided into 2 classes: Class 2 (ending -ã) and Class 3 (ending -e)
- Pronouns: \bar{n} = 1SG, $\bar{e}h$ = 3SG, both of which are in Class 3
- |V agrees with the subject
- kV precedes the object and agrees with it
- tV ... kV agree with the head noun
- |V agrees with the possessed noun

Verbs

- \acute{n} for the present, \grave{a} for the past
- The negative particle is ||qhúa

Example sentences

- $\bar{e}h \grave{a} ||qhúa káni + kã \ddot{t}gúã ||qhaã + tã ||xãã \grave{a} kùhm kã$ = He did not want another egg that the men had touched.
 - ||qhúa = negative particle
 - \grave{a} = signifies the sentence is in the past tense
 - $\bar{e}h$ = noun of the sentence (He) belonging to the third class (Class 3)
- $qáe |ã ||gãã tã \bar{e}h \acute{n} |nãa kã \grave{a} dt'kx'ába ke dõ'le$ = The woman's springbok [that he looks at] was stuck on the grass.
 - $qáe$ = the noun of the sentence; woman/mother (depending on context)
 - \grave{a} = signifies the sentence is in the past tense
 - $ã$ = the noun belongs to the second class (Class 2)

Numbers and Quantifiers

- Taa only has three native numbers:
 - 1 = $\ddot{t}ûã$
 - 2 = $\ddot{t}núm$
 - 3 = $llâe$
 - Numbers 4 and above are loans from foreign languages, such as Tswana and Kgalagadi
- Within a sentence, numbers come after the noun they apply to
- The quantifier 'all' is identified by codes determined by its placement either before or after a noun. This system is only concerned about pragmatically unmarked contexts of the quantifier placement, where:

- Code 1 = when the quantifier ‘all’ comes **before** the noun
- Code 2 = when the quantifier ‘all’ comes **after** the noun
- Code 3 = when the quantifier ‘all’ can come before **OR** after the noun
- Code 0 = when the quantifier ‘all’ **isn’t used** next to nouns
- Code ? = when there is **no mention** of quantifiers at all
- The quantifier ‘teqhou’, meaning ‘all,’ generally precedes the noun they apply to:
 - **Keik leak teqhou naq an sa tol**
IMP:1PL.EXCL go all COMPL to LOC inland
‘We all went inland.’ (Macdonald 2010: 164)
 - This includes a code 1 quantifier
- The quantifier ‘alauriyekye’, also meaning ‘all’, can be placed before or after the noun it applies to; therefore, it is coded 3.

Taa noun class system

Taa has five noun classes (labeled 1–5), which are distinguished by grammatical gender and number. These classes govern agreement across pronouns, numerals, adjectives, and verbs through prefixes, suffixes, or tone patterns.

- **Class 1**
 - Typically includes inanimate or abstract nouns, often singular.
 - Agreement: Marker -a (singular), tone-based in some contexts.
 - Example: llxai-a (‘thing’, class 1) → llxai-a ʔ”u-a (‘one thing’), where ʔ”u-a agrees with class 1 marker -a.
- **Class 2**
 - Often inanimate plurals or specific animates; less common.
 - Agreement: Marker -i or tone variation.
 - Example: llxai-ni ʔnûm (‘two things’), where ʔnûm (two) is invariant, no agreement required.
- **Class 3**
 - Common for singular human-like nouns (e.g., people, kinship terms).
 - Agreement: Marker -e (singular).
 - Example: ʔqaqe ʔ”u-e (‘one child’), with ʔ”u-e showing class 3 agreement via -e.

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